

Research Article

Nanoscale chemical segregation to twin interfaces in τ -MnAl-C and resulting effects on the magnetic propertiesPanpan Zhao^{a,b,*}, Markus Gusenbauer^c, Harald Oezelt^c, Daniel Wolf^a, Thomas Gemming^a, Thomas Schrefl^c, Kornelius Nielsch^{a,b}, Thomas George Woodcock^{a,*}^a Leibniz IFW Dresden, Helmholtzstr. 20, Dresden 01069, Germany^b TU Dresden, Institute of Materials Science, Dresden 01062, Germany^c Department for Integrated Sensor Systems, Danube University Krems, Krems an der Donau 3500, Austria

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ABSTRACT

In this study, aberration-corrected scanning transmission electron microscopy coupled with electron energy-loss spectroscopy (STEM-EELS) was used to investigate the atomistic structure and chemical composition of true twin and order twin boundaries in ferromagnetic τ -MnAl-C. True twins and order twins were distinguished based on the diffraction patterns using TEM. No elemental segregation was observed at the coherent true twin boundary but some Mn enrichment within a region of about 1.5–2 nm was found at the incoherent true twin boundary. A transition region with Mn enrichment about 4–6 nm wide was found at the order twin boundary. A carbon cluster with a size of around 5 nm was also found at the twin boundary. Micromagnetic simulations were conducted to study the effect of this chemical segregation at twin interfaces on the magnetic properties. The results showed that the coercivity tends to increase with increasing structural and chemical disorder at the interface.

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1. Introduction

The microstructure of the promising rare-earth-free permanent magnet, τ -MnAl-C, is characterized by a variety of defects, among which, twin boundaries are frequently observed [1–8]. Twin boundaries have a limiting effect on the extrinsic magnetic properties of the material: the remanence is reduced due to the large misorientation of the magnetically easy $\langle 001 \rangle$ axes of the parent and the twin, and both experiments and micromagnetic simulations show that the coercivity is reduced because twin boundaries exhibit a small pinning force for magnetic domain walls [9–16]. Recently, Palanisamy et al. [2,17] reported a significant Mn segregation at twin boundaries in τ -MnAl using atom probe tomography (APT). In the center of a twin, the composition was similar to that of the parent region, but on approaching either twin boundary from inside the twin, a Mn-enriched layer was observed, followed by a Mn-depleted layer on the other side of the boundary [2]. For

narrow twins (~ 6 nm in width), the Mn-enriched regions at the twin boundaries were so close together that the entire twin appeared to be Mn-rich [2]. The degree of depletion or enrichment of Mn was observed to vary with distance parallel to the twin boundary [17]. Such elemental segregations at grain boundaries or twin boundaries are generally of great interest as the material performance could be altered by orders of magnitude [18–20]. The intrinsic magnetic properties of τ phase are sensitive to composition changes: Pareti et al. [21] reported that an increase in Mn content in the τ phase would lead to an increase in Curie temperature and a decrease in the saturation magnetization. As a result, differences in the Mn-content at twin boundaries would change the intrinsic magnetic properties of the τ -phase locally and may thus affect the energetics of nucleation and pinning of magnetic domain walls at twin boundaries.

Bittner et al. [1] found the existence of three different types of twins in both the as-transformed and hot deformed τ -MnAl-C using electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD). They are described as true twins, order twins and pseudo twins with misorientation angles 180° , 118° and 62° about the normal to $\{111\}$, respectively. As the atomistic structure of the interface is expected to be different for these three types of twins [1], it is reasonable to expect that

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any elemental segregation behavior may also be different; however, this has not been investigated to date. A further aspect which is currently unknown is the possible segregation of C to interfaces in C-containing MnAl-based alloys. The C-content is also known to affect the intrinsic properties [21].

The current work aims to provide an independent confirmation, using STEM-EELS, of the elemental segregation at twin boundaries in τ -MnAl reported using APT by Palanisamy et al. [2,17], and to extend the investigation to different types of twin boundaries and to the distribution of C. In addition, micromagnetic simulations based closely on the experimental results will be carried out in order to determine the effect of the elemental segregation at twin boundaries on the magnetic properties.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and characterization methods

An alloy with a nominal composition of $\text{Mn}_{53}\text{Al}_{45}\text{C}_2$ (at.%) was prepared by induction melting of the high purity elemental starting materials (99.99% Mn, 99.99% Al and 99.9% C) under argon atmosphere. In order to obtain the τ phase, the as-cast sample was encapsulated in a quartz tube filled with pure Ar at a back pressure of 150 mbar, homogenized at 1100°C for 2 days, followed by air cooling to room temperature. Markers were made on the polished sample by a hardness tester and the orientation of grains close to the markers was mapped using a Zeiss Gemini Leo 1530 scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD) detector (Oxford Instruments). An evenly spaced grid of measurement points with a spacing of 1 μm was chosen, yielding in total 200×200 data points for each mapping area.

The EBSD data was used to identify the sites of specific twin boundaries and TEM lamellae were prepared from these positions using the focused ion beam (FIB) on an FEI Helios Nanolab Dual Beam FIB with the standard lift-out technique. The lamellae were thinned to electron transparency also using the FIB. After FIB preparation, the TEM samples were milled for 4 min with Ar-ions at 0.1 keV using Gatan PIPS II. The diffraction patterns of the twin interfaces were acquired using an FEI Tecnai G² microscope operated at 200 kV. For all the diffraction analysis, the $tP4$ representation of the $L1_0$ unit cell ($a=b=3.92$ Å, $c=3.57$ Å, $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90^\circ$) was used.

Before starting STEM-EELS experiments, the lamellae were plasma cleaned for 5–15 min to remove hydrocarbon contamination attached to the sample surface. The STEM-EELS experiment was performed on a double-corrected FEI Titan³ 80–300 transmission electron microscope with a Schottky-type electron source, a DCOR probe corrector (CEOS Company, Heidelberg) and a Gatan Imaging Filter (GIF) Tridiem model 863 electron energy-loss spectrometer. The microscope was operated at 300 kV at a semi-convergence angle of 21.3 mrad and the current was set to be about 100–125 pA. The camera length used to acquire the HAADF-STEM image of the twin boundary was 115 mm. EELS linescans and mapping were acquired in order to extract the chemical composition across the twin interfaces. In order to increase EELS collection efficiency, a collection semi-angle of 43.1 mrad was selected resulting in an energy resolution of 1.5 eV. The spectrometer was set to an energy dispersion of 0.1 eV/channel, and the dwell time for Mn-L, Al-K and C-K edges were 1000, 5000 and 500 ms, respectively. In order to exclude the possible influence of variations in the sample thickness on the EELS chemical profiles, the reduced thickness, t/λ_p , where λ_p is the inelastic mean free electron path length, was determined from the EELS data for each linescan using the method shown in Ref. [22]. The variation of t/λ_p as a function of distance along the linescan across the order twin boundary is

shown exemplarily in Fig. S1 in Supplementary Information. The data show that the variation of the sample thickness around the middle 30 nm of the linescan, where the boundary was located, is approximately $\pm 0.02 \lambda_p$. This is not considered to be a significant thickness variation. It is assumed here that λ_p is independent of changes in the chemical composition. Similar t/λ_p data were collected for the other regions analyzed and all these results indicated that the EELS chemical profiles were not affected by variation of the thickness of the lamella.

2.2. Data processing

To cross check the reliability of EELS data analysis, three methods were compared: (1) the conventional edge intensity integration method with background subtraction and signal integration after core loss edge using the open source software Hyperspy [23]; (2) EEL spectrum fitting with Hyperspy; (3) EEL spectrum fitting with EELSMODEL [24]. All these three methods present very similar results (the distribution of Mn across the order twin boundary is shown as an example in Fig. S2) and the first method was used to extract the elemental distribution at the twin boundaries.

In order to improve the signal to background ratio of Al and Mn spectra and to include a large twin boundary region, EELS mapping over an area of 50×10 measurement positions was conducted across the twin boundary. The mapped area can also be considered as 10 linescans perpendicular to the twin boundary. The step size for EELS data acquisition in this direction was set to be 0.5 or 1 nm and in order to reduce any possible contamination effect from the previous linescan, the distance between each linescan was about 6 nm (please see Fig. S3 as an example). Sample drift during data acquisition was recorded for every 50 measurements to monitor the stability of the holder as shown in Fig. S4. The maximum integrated intensity of EEL spectrum changes at the boundary if elemental segregation occurs. Therefore, EELS data alignment could be conducted based on the changes of maximum integrated intensity of EEL spectrum using Hyperspy. The EELS data was then summed up after data alignment and averaged along the boundary which would be equivalent to a single linescan with a large twin boundary region represented. The elemental distribution then can be obtained using conventional edge intensity integration using Hyperspy. Details can be found in Fig. S3 taking the EELS mapping for Al across the order twin boundary as an example.

2.3. Micromagnetic simulation

Demagnetization curves of the different twin types with their respective Mn enrichment close to the twin boundaries were computed and compared to those from ideal structures with a homogeneous material distribution. To avoid corner and edge effects [25], a spherical finite element model with a diameter of 40 nm was chosen (Fig. 1 on the left). The sphere is split by a twin boundary and contains a Mn-enriched layer, a Mn-depleted layer and bulk layer on each half. To simulate the case where no chemical segregation was observed, homogeneous material properties were adopted throughout the system. Where chemical segregation was observed, different intrinsic magnetic properties for the Mn-depleted and Mn-enriched regions were applied. The mesh size is chosen such that the largest finite element (tetrahedron) is smaller than the characteristic length of the material [11] as well as to represent the thin layers close to the twin boundary. An adaptive mesh size, from 0.5 nm at the Mn-enriched and Mn-depleted layers to 3 nm at bulk, was used.

The model is computed by a micromagnetic solver, which calculates the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation on a tetrahedral finite element grid [26]. For computing the demagnetization curve, the external field, H_{ext} , is swept from +4 T to -4 T in 200 ns. For

Fig. 1. Left: Finite element micromagnetic model of twin boundary and segregation layers. Right: External field directions evenly distributed around a unit sphere with the simulation model in the center.

Fig. 2. Orientation maps of the as-transformed τ -MnAlC showing the angle between the $\langle 100 \rangle$ axis of the τ -phase and the reference X-axis (a) and the angle between the $\langle 001 \rangle$ axis of the τ -phase and the reference Z-axis (b). Three different types of twin boundaries are determined based on the misorientation difference (c). The different coloured interfaces in (c) correspond to pseudo twins (dark green), order twins (red) and true twins (blue); other grain boundaries appear black.

each twin model, demagnetization curves for about 1000 different field directions, distributed evenly around a unit sphere (Fibonacci Sphere, Fig. 1 on the right) were computed [27]. In such a way, the switching field H_c distribution of the different twin boundaries can be compared. The switching field was defined as the critical field at which the largest step in the demagnetization curve is observed. Using this definition, the switching field was related to the irreversible magnetization reversal [10]. The number of simulations can be partially reduced by symmetry properties of the models, i.e., when the magnetostatic easy axis directions are aligned in a certain plane. To check whether the results depend on the number of field directions used for plotting the distributions, 10x more external field values on the unit sphere were computed for the true coherent model. The resulting distribution characteristics did not change decisively and therefore the number of simulations for each model was maintained at about 1000.

3. Results and discussion

In the ferromagnetic tetragonal τ -phase, twin boundaries are found in both the as-transformed and hot deformed states. Based on the misorientation difference about $\{111\}$, three different types of twins are categorized and they are true twins, order twins and pseudo twins with the misorientation angle 180° , 118° and 62° correspondingly as shown in Fig. 2. As true twins and order twins

occupy more than 90% of the total twin types [1], detailed microstructure, elemental segregations and micromagnetic properties are studied here.

3.1. Order twin

All the peaks in the X-ray diffractogram of the as-transformed MnAl-C alloy can be identified as τ phase (see Fig. S5), and the lattice parameters expressed in the $tP4$ unit cell are: $a = 0.392$ nm and $c = 0.357$ nm. An order twin was located on the sample using EBSD and the twin type was unambiguously confirmed, based on a series of selected area diffraction (SAD) patterns carried out on a TEM lamella extracted from the same twin boundary (see Fig. S6). Fig. 3 shows the high-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) images of the order twin boundary with the beam direction parallel to $\langle 011 \rangle$. A bright region was observed at the order twin boundary as shown in Fig. 3(a) and the lattice planes appear to be continuous across the order twin boundary (Fig. 3(b)). It has been shown that this variation in HAADF intensity across the boundary is not due to changes in sample thickness (see Section 2.1). Higher HAADF intensity, therefore, indicates the presence of a larger fraction of atoms with larger elastic scattering cross sections, which suggests that the bright region of the order twin boundary may be enriched in Mn. The bottom left corner of Fig. 3(b) shows the fast Fourier transformation

Fig. 3. HAADF-STEM image of the order twin boundary in τ -MnAl-C. (a, b) HAADF images of order twin interface at low and high magnifications. The inset in the bottom left corner of Fig. 3(b) shows the fast Fourier transformation (FFT) of the whole image; (c, d) the inverse fast Fourier transformation (IFFT) of the masked 200 and 100 spots; (e, f) the enlarged areas of the HAADF-STEM image in Fig. 3(b) marked with dashed red and bright rectangles; (g, h) integrated HAADF intensity profiles along (200) lattice planes in Fig. 3(e) and (f) marked with red and bright rectangles.

(FFT) of the whole image. Interestingly, weak spots belonging to the spacing of (100) and (011) planes are observed in the FFT. In order to reveal the locations in the image where the spatial frequencies corresponding to the extra spots contribute, Fourier-filtered images i.e. the inverse fast Fourier transformation (IFFT) of masked regions of the FFT containing the (200) and (100) spots were calculated and are shown in Fig. 3(c) and (d). In the IFFT of the masked (200) spots, the intensity has a homogeneous distribution over the whole image and the bright fringes are continuous across the interface. These fringes correspond to the (200) planes, which are also visible in Fig. 3(b). In contrast, in the IFFT of the masked (100) spots (Fig. 3(d)), the intensity is the highest in the bright region of the order twin boundary (cf. Fig. 3(b)). Although some intensity resulting from the (100) spots is observed in Fig.

3(d) in the regions far from the order twin boundary, the absolute values of the intensity are several times lower than those near the interface. This implies that the occurrence of the weak (100) spots in the FFT of the HAADF image of Fig. 3(b) results mostly from the bright region of the order twin boundary. Similar analysis was carried out with the (022) and (011) spots and this also revealed that the weak, extra spots were sourced mainly from the bright region of the order twin boundary (see Fig. S7). The presence of the extra spots in the FFT implies that the HAADF intensity of neighboring (200) and (022) planes must alternate between two different values in the bright region of the order twin boundary. In order to investigate this, the integrated HAADF intensity in the red and bright rectangles in Fig. 3(e) and (f), corresponding to (200) planes, was extracted and is shown in Fig. 3(g) and (h). Ev-

Fig. 4. Atomistic models of the order twin interface in (a) $\langle 0\bar{1}1 \rangle$ viewing direction and (b) $\langle 010 \rangle$ viewing direction. The position of the order twin boundary is marked with black arrows. The upward vector of the left grain in Fig. 4(a) is parallel to $[011]$ and the upward vector of the right grain is parallel to $[101]$. In Fig. 4(b), the upward vector of the left grain is parallel to $[001]$, while the upward vector of the right grain shows a slight deviation to $[100]$ (about 5.4° around $[010]$).

every second (200) plane shows similar HAADF intensity and different HAADF intensity could be observed between the neighboring lattice planes; whereas, in the area away from the bright region as shown in Fig. 3(h), the neighboring planes of atom columns show similar HAADF intensity. A similar result was obtained for the (022) lattice planes (see Fig. S7). The slightly different HAADF intensity of consecutive (200) and (022) planes in the bright region of the order twin boundary implies that differences in the chemical composition of neighboring lattice planes exist. These could result from a longer-range chemical ordering which is not consistent with the $L1_0$ structure. The weaker and inhomogeneous distribution of the intensity arising from the (100) and (011) spots far from the order twin interface and the presence of discontinuities in the bright fringes, marked by the black arrows in Fig. 3(d), indicate that this longer-range chemical ordering is far less pronounced at distances from the order twin boundary. This is also supported by the SAD patterns in Fig. S6(c) and (d), which show that the extra (100) and (011) spots are not present in the bulk of the grains and that these exhibit the expected $L1_0$ ordering.

The order twin has the orientation relationship $[\bar{1}01]//[01\bar{1}]$ and $(111)//(111)$ and the interface is partially incoherent, due to the deviation of the c/a ratio of the $tP4$ unit cell from unity: the c/a ratio of the τ phase is around 0.911. This partial incoherency can be observed by viewing an atomistic model in different orientations (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 5 shows the averaged HAADF intensity extracted across the order twin boundary in Fig. 3(a) and also the average integrated intensity of the Mn-L_{2,3} and Al-K edges, obtained from EELS data (see Section 2.2) across the order twin boundary. In the top image of Fig. 5, a higher HAADF intensity could be observed at the order twin boundary with a thickness of about 4, 5 nm, bounded by regions of lower HAADF intensity on both sides with a thickness of about 4 nm. A sharp Mn signal increase can be observed at the order twin boundary with a thickness of about 6 nm and slight Mn deficiency, which is more pronounced on the left of the order twin boundary, could also be found. Correspondingly, a dramatic reduction of Al signal was observed at the order twin boundary with a thickness of about 4 nm and slight Al enrichment was found on both sides of the order twin boundary with a thickness of 3–4 nm. The chemical profiles of Mn and Al are consistent with the variation of the HAADF signal: where excess Al is present, the smaller elastic scattering cross section of that element leads to a lower HAADF intensity, whereas where excess Mn is present, the larger elastic scattering cross section of Mn atoms produces higher HAADF intensity. Compared with the integrated intensity of the Mn signal, the absolute values of the integrated intensity of the

Al signal are smaller which results from the high energy loss position of the Al K-edge ($\Delta E = 1560$ eV). The results here show relative changes in the concentrations of the elements rather than absolute composition values. The three data sets in Fig. 5 were obtained from different regions of the same order twin boundary but are self-consistent in showing the Mn-enriched region at the order twin, surrounded by an Al-enriched region on both sides.

Fig. 5. Averaged HAADF intensity extracted across the order twin boundary in Fig. 3(a) (top) and the average integrated intensity of the Mn-L_{2,3} (middle) and Al-K edges (bottom), obtained from EELS data across the order twin boundary.

Fig. 6. HAADF-STEM image of a true twin boundary. (a) HAADF-STEM image of a true twin at low magnification; (b, c) HAADF-HRSTEM images of a coherent true twin interface and an incoherent true twin interface; (d, e) atomistic models of the coherent true twin in (011) and $\langle 2\bar{1}1 \rangle$ viewing directions; (f, g) atomistic models of the incoherent true twin in (011) and $\langle 2\bar{1}1 \rangle$ viewing directions. The position of the twin boundary is marked with black arrows.

The profiles in Fig. 5 are similar to those reported by Palanisamy et al. for a narrow twin [2]; however, in the case of a narrow twin, two twin boundaries are present, whereas a single order twin boundary was present in the region investigated here in Fig. 5. Order twin boundaries may form during the massive transformation from ϵ to τ if two growing regions of τ with different orientations impinge. If each growth front has a Mn-enriched region followed by a Mn-depleted region, the formation of the order twin boundary would result in the chemical profiles observed.

3.2. True twin

A region containing the true twins was located on the sample using EBSD and the twin types were unambiguously determined from SAD patterns of a TEM lamella extracted from the same region (see Fig. S8). Fig. 6(a) shows the HAADF-STEM image of the

prepared true twin lamella with the two twin boundaries of interest, a coherent true twin boundary (CTB) where the misorientation is that of a true twin and the boundary plane is {111} and an incoherent true twin boundary (ICTB) where the misorientation is that of a true twin but the boundary plane is not {111}. The coherent true twin boundary marked by the dashed white circle in Fig. 6(a) corresponds to the interface of grain 1 and grain 3 shown in Fig. S8(b), while the incoherent true twin boundary marked by a dashed white circle in Fig. 6(a) corresponds to the boundary perpendicular to the left boundary of grain 2 shown in Fig. S8(b). From the high resolution STEM images with the zone axis parallel to [011] shown in Fig. 6(b), a mirror plane {111} can be observed for the coherent true twin boundary and the misorientation angle can be described as $71.33^\circ//[011]$. The STEM image of the incoherent twin boundary is shown in Fig. 6(c). The coherency of the coherent true twin and incoherent true twin boundary could

Fig. 7. Average integrated intensity of the Mn-L_{2,3} (top) and Al-K edges (bottom) obtained from EELS data across the incoherent true twin interface.

be further elucidated in the atomistic models in Fig. 6(d–f). In the tetragonal τ phase, the angle between the (011) and (21 $\bar{1}$) planes is about 93.2° and the incoherent true twin boundary could be approximately described as $\Sigma 3$ {112} incoherent true twin boundary (ICTB). The ICTB was found to be three (21 $\bar{1}$) atomic layers thick. Research for FCC materials with low stacking fault energy, shows that the width of $\Sigma 3$ {112} boundaries is usually larger [28–30]. In the as-transformed τ phase, stacking faults could be easily observed, which implies the stacking fault energy of τ -MnAl-C is low [31,32]. In this case, wide $\Sigma 3$ {112} boundaries would be expected in tetragonal τ -MnAl-C, similarly to the case for FCC metals; however, a width of three atomic layers was observed here. The reason why the $\Sigma 3$ {112} boundary is narrow despite the low stacking

fault energy of the τ -phase may be related to the energy difference of partial dislocations in the τ phase. Due to the tetragonal structure of the τ phase, not all partial dislocations are equivalent: the $\langle 112 \rangle$ partial dislocation is more energetically favorable than $\langle 121 \rangle$ [33]. As a result, the movement of $\langle 121 \rangle$ partial dislocations for the formation of twins will require higher energy and this may have a limiting effect on the boundary width.

To study the elemental distribution at ICTB and CTB, EELS mapping was also conducted across the true twin boundaries. The Mn and Al contents across the ICTB are shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen that, similarly to the order twin, the ICTB shows a Mn-enriched region at the interface surrounded by Mn-depleted regions on both sides. An ICTB may form in a similar way to an order twin, where two regions of τ with different orientations impinge during the massive transformation, thus leading to similar chemical profiles.

The width of these regions in the ICTB is smaller than that in the order twin boundary (cf. Figs. 7 and 5). It is interesting to note that the Al profile does not show a peak on the left of the boundary. The Al and Mn EELS data were necessarily collected from different positions on the same boundary and this is likely to be the source of the discrepancy between the Mn and Al profiles in Fig. 7. It has previously been shown that the chemical composition varies parallel to the twin boundary [17]. By comparing the chemical distribution at the order twin boundary and incoherent true twin boundary, it can be observed that the intensity of the Mn EELS signal at the order twin boundary is 1.5 times the Mn intensity of the region away from the boundary (Fig. 5), while the same measure is only 1.17 for the incoherent true twin boundary. This implies that the Mn segregation at the order twin boundary is larger than that for the incoherent true twin boundary (Fig. 7). This result could also be confirmed from the Al signal at the order twin boundary and the incoherent true twin boundary: the Al signal at the order twin boundary is 0.78 times the value away from the order twin boundary, while for the incoherent true twin boundary, the value is 0.85 which implies higher Al content at the incoherent true twin boundary.

Fig. 8(a) shows the HAADF-STEM image of a coherent true twin boundary. EELS mapping was performed in the marked orange box with a length of about 25 nm perpendicular to the boundary. The true twin boundary marked by a dashed white line is located at around 13.3 nm. The sample drift data during EELS acquisition of the coherent true twin boundary is shown in Fig. S4(c). As no signal changes at the CTB, it is impractical to do any alignment.

Fig. 8. EELS analysis of Mn across a coherent true twin interface. (a) HAADF-STEM image of coherent true twin interface with orange mapping area and yellow drift reference area. The dashed white line shows the position of the coherent true twin interface; (b) average integrated intensity of the Mn-L_{2,3} edges obtained from EELS data across the coherent true twin interface and dashed red line was shown as the position of the coherent true twin interface.

Fig. 9. EEL spectra of τ -MnAl-C for Mn $L_{2,3}$ edge located at three different positions across the order twin boundary (a), incoherent true twin boundary (b) and coherent true twin boundary (c), respectively. The EEL spectra in red, blue and green colors in Fig. 9(a–c) are located at the left part of the twin boundary, at the twin boundary and at the right part of the twin boundary.

Fig. 10. Chemical distribution of carbon across the order twin interface. (a) A map showing the intensity of EEL spectra (integrated between $\Delta E=180$ eV and $\Delta E=385$ eV) recorded at different positions x and y relative to the order twin interface, which was oriented vertically. The x and y axes in (a) are perpendicular and parallel to the twin boundary respectively; (b) the EEL spectrum (red line) from the top left pixel in (a) showing the background subtraction process using the power law model (blue curve) and the red shaded region is the background fit window; (c, d) line profiles at different positions, y , along the order twin interface showing the integrated intensity of the C K-edge after background subtraction as a function of distance across the interface.

Considering the high stability of the specimen perpendicular to the boundary from the 1st to the 4th linescan marked in the light green region (Fig. S4(c)), these linescans were used to extract the Mn distribution across CTB without any data alignment using Hyperspy and the result is shown in Fig. 8(b). No variation in the Mn-signal is found at the coherent true twin boundary, which is located at 13.3 nm. For reference, the largest variation of the Mn intensity from the mean value at the CTB is approximately 0.05, whereas the Mn trace at the order twin and ICTB showed variations of 0.6 and 0.4 respectively from the mean value. These different degrees of chemical segregation can also be seen in the EEL spectra showing the Mn $L_{2,3}$ core loss edges at various positions relative to the twin boundary as shown in Fig. 9. From the above

analysis, it can be seen that the strength of chemical segregation to the twin interface decreases with the decreasing degree of structural disorder going from the order twin boundary to the incoherent true twin boundary to the coherent true twin boundary.

The formation of true twins may come from two different transformation mechanisms: massive transformation or displacive-diffusion transformation [3,34–37]. True twins formed by the shear mode are less likely to show any elemental segregations because the formation process does not necessarily include simultaneous diffusion. For true twins formed via the massive transformation mode, it has been reported that short range diffusion processes occur simultaneously with atomic attachment faults which lead to twin formation [2]. Although it was not explicitly stated, the twins

Table 1

The assumed intrinsic properties of τ phase with different Mn content used as input for the micromagnetic twin models.

	Location	Composition	$\mu_0 M_s$ (T)	K_1 (MJ m ⁻³)	A (pJ m ⁻¹)
Bulk properties	Far from twins	Mn ₅₅ Al ₄₅	0.8	1.3	20
True coherent	Everywhere	Mn ₅₅ Al ₄₅	0.8	1.3	20
True incoherent	At boundary (Mn-enriched)	Mn _{62.5} Al _{37.5}	0.62	1.87	12.01
True incoherent	Transition (Mn-depleted)	Mn ₅₂ Al ₄₈	0.87	1.07	23.65
Order	At boundary (Mn-enriched)	Mn _{73.5} Al _{26.5}	0.36	2.7	4.05
Order	Transition (Mn-depleted)	Mn ₅₂ Al ₄₈	0.87	1.07	23.65

Table 2

Simulation models with their respective twin configuration (directions of the easy axes in A and B given in Cartesian coordinates, angles α between the two easy axes, thicknesses of Mn-enriched layer d_1 and Mn-depleted layers d_2 , and an image of the model with the respective easy axes).

Simulation model name	α	d_1	d_2	Model
True coherent	75.66° (104.34°)	x	x	
True incoherent	75.66° (104.34°)	2 nm	2 nm	
True incoherent (para)	75.66° (104.34°)	2 nm (air)	2 nm (air)	
True incoherent (same)	75.66° (104.34°)	x	x	
Order incoherent (same)	95.35° (84.65°)	x	x	
Order incoherent	95.35° (84.65°)	5 nm	3 nm	
Order incoherent (para)	95.35° (84.65°)	5 nm (air)	3 nm (air)	

studied in Refs. [2,17] appear to be true twins. As no chemical segregation was found at the true twin measured in the current work, it seems reasonable to conclude that the true twin formed via shear. The different formation mechanisms explain the differences in the chemical profiles between the true twins measured here and those measured in Refs. [2,17], which were thought to form via the massive transformation.

3.3. Carbon segregation at twin boundaries

In the previous sections, the Mn and Al distributions at twin boundaries have been investigated. The alloys used here additionally contained carbon and so the distribution of that element is also of interest. Measuring the C distribution is non-trivial because the carbon signal can be originated from two sources: the carbon in the alloy and carbon contamination during the sample preparation process. In order to reduce the influence of carbon contamination, the sample was plasma cleaned for 10–15 min before doing STEM-EELS experiment. Fig. 10(a) shows the integrated intensity

of EEL spectrum of the whole mapping area with the order twin boundary located at 25 nm (the whole morphology of the carbon mapping region in Fig. S9). A bright area was observed at the center of Fig. 10(a). The length of the EELS mapping area was around 50 nm perpendicular to the boundary. The specimen drift during the whole EEL spectra acquisition was within 2.2 nm as shown in Fig. S4(f). The step size used for the carbon K-edge acquisition was set to be 1 nm and no data alignment was performed. The EEL spectra were then summed up and averaged in the direction parallel to the twin boundary and the background subtraction before the carbon K-edge is shown in Fig. 10(b). A faint carbon K-edge signal can be observed above the blue power law background curve located at 280–300 eV. After background subtraction and signal integration, Fig. 10(c) shows the carbon distribution across the order twin boundary and it can be seen carbon segregation occurs at the order twin boundary within a region of about 5 nm. Combining the results in Fig. 10(a) and (c), it can be concluded that a carbon cluster exists at the order twin boundary. Fig. 10(d) shows the carbon content signal of the order twin boundary in another region with

Fig. 11. Switching field H_c visualized on a globe unit sphere of the true coherent model. Each colored spot represents the switching field H_c of a simulation with the respective unique external field direction (compare Fig. 1 on the right). The simulation model with the respective easy axes and the segregation layers are shown in the top left corner. The colors of this model are arbitrary and used to distinguish between the bulk phases and the segregation layers within the model. The easy axes are lying on the x-z plane, whereas the twin boundary lies on the y-z plane. Demagnetization curves with the external field H_{ext} and the normalized magnetization M/M_s are shown for certain spots on the globe.

Fig. 12. Comparison of different twin models. The red bars indicate the mean and standard deviations and the black lines median and max/min values of the switching field H_c .

the same experimental parameters and post data processing and it is difficult to say whether there is any carbon segregation at the order twin boundary in this region. Palanisamy et al. [2,17] reported the inhomogeneous distribution of Mn along the twin boundaries. These results show the distribution of carbon is also inhomogeneous along the twin boundary.

3.4. Micromagnetic simulations

Table 1 shows the intrinsic magnetic properties which were used to describe the τ phase with different Mn content in the twin boundary models. The compositions of Mn enriched and depleted regions were estimated based on the EELS analysis assuming that the region far away from the boundary had a composition of $Mn_{55}Al_{45}$. It was assumed that the τ phase remains ferromagnetic even in the regions with different compositions and an estimate of how the intrinsic magnetic properties of MnAl might change with composition was based on measurements of similar variations in MnGa [38].

Table 2 gives information on the different simulation models including the easy axis configuration and the thickness of the Mn-enriched (d1) and Mn-depleted (d2) layers (compare Fig. 1 on the left). The “true coherent” and “same” models have homogeneous material parameters throughout the system. In other cases, a Mn-enriched region at the twin boundary followed by Mn-depleted regions to each side of the sphere is included. The rest of the sphere has bulk properties. The simulation models with the term “para” indicate the extreme case, where it was assumed that the material in the regions of different Mn compositions is no longer ferromagnetic i.e. a paramagnetic phase exists between the two halves of the sphere, which is modelled by an air gap. The order twin models have the same geometry and easy axes configuration, whereas the true twin models differ in the twin plane as well as in the easy axis configuration.

A visual output of the true coherent model is shown on a colored unit sphere whereby the color encodes the switching field (Fig. 11). Each spot represents the direction of the external

field direction for the particular simulation (compare Fig. 1 on the right). For certain interesting points, the demagnetization curve is given for a detailed comparison. Please note that the switching field H_c is defined as the largest step in the curve. The calculated values of H_c do not include the effects of magnetostatic interactions between neighboring grains and therefore tend to be higher than those typically measured in experiments for bulk samples. The easy axis configuration with the twin boundary is shown in the top left corner of Fig. 11.

The results of the micromagnetic simulations (Fig. 12) show that the coherent true twin has the lowest switching field of all the twin boundary configurations studied here. The experimental results shown above demonstrate that such boundaries also show the lowest degree of structural and chemical disorder. For the incoherent true twin, increasing H_c was observed with increasing simulated chemical disorder, i.e. from true incoherent (same) to true incoherent and true incoherent (para). A similar trend was observed for the order twin, leading to the conclusion that the observed chemical disorder at twin interfaces acts to enhance the coercivity of the material.

4. Conclusion

In τ -MnAl-C ($c/a=0.91$, $tP4$ unit cell), increasing structural disorder is expected going from coherent true twin boundary to incoherent true twin boundary to the order twin boundary. This was observed in HAADF-HRSTEM images where a mirror plane was present for the coherent true twin boundary, a transition region, several atomic layers thick, existed for the incoherent true twin boundary and a thicker transition region, about 4–6 nm, was found in the case of the order twin boundary. The disorder at different types of twin boundaries is also associated with the degree of segregation of the constituent elements. By using STEM-EELS, higher Mn enrichment and Al deficiency were observed at the order twin boundary with a thickness of about 6 nm, slight Mn segregation was observed at the incoherent true twin boundary with a reduced thickness about 1.5–2 nm and no segregation was found at the coherent true twin boundary. In addition, the distribution of carbon is inhomogeneous across the twin boundary and carbon clusters were found. Micromagnetic simulations revealed the effect of the different segregation layers on the magnetic properties of the examined twin boundaries. For both the true and order twin models, an increase in switching field was observed with the increasing chemical segregation observed in the experiments. These results suggest that targeted doping of interfaces in τ -MnAl may be a promising strategy to increase the coercivity of the material for applications.

Data availability

The data are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.jmst.2022.05.052.

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